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Digital Governance: A Pathway To Inclusivity And Development

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Introduction

The expeditious growth of Africa's population, as well as the opportunities and challenges this poses in terms of education and training of the African youth have pointed to ever -growing interdependencies between the pivotal role of information and communication technology (ICT) and harnessing the potential of the internet. The mutual entanglement of both spheres manifests on many levels with digital governance being a vital enabler. The recent rise of big data and computational techniques have brought about new opportunities for participation, organizing and collective action by citizens. If the 20th century engineers of consent had magnifying glasses and baseball bats, those of the 21st century have acquired telescopes, microscopes and scalpels in the shape of digital technologies and analytics¹. These new technologies hold incredible promise for human welfare. They offer us powerful new ways to achieve our shared commitments to each and every one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), a set of 17 socioeconomic, political and environmental objectives forming and structuring the development agenda of the next 10 years². Against this background, a question one may ask is: what role can the internet ecosystem community play to make this world a better place? Can digital technologies of the big data era, and the opportunities, risks and questions they raise, be leveraged as forces of positive disruption?³

This paper outlines approaches for greater transparency and improved governance of the internet to promote inclusivity and development using learnings from the modules. It makes a case that governance of internet (and by algorithms) goes beyond regulating the design and implementation of code and the technology itself and involves a wider evidence-based approach relying on risk and impact assessments, organizational approaches, and business models and strategies. The paper also focuses on the governing effects of internet algorithms in information societies.

Role of governments, UN agencies and other stakeholders

As learned during the course, the WSIS Geneva Plan of Action highlighted the role of governments and all stakeholders in the promotion of ICTs for development, suggesting that they explore the viability of establishing multi-stakeholder portals at the national level. In this plan of action, capacity building is highlighted, calling for the launch of inclusive education and training programs which provide opportunities to fully participate in the information society and is reflective of concerns of the local community. More of this is further emphasized in the week three module where some governments are experimenting with the multi-stakeholder model for domestic internet policy-making. For example, Canada's innovative approach to securing the Internet of Things is using a multi-stakeholder process. This reinforces the need for African governments to follow up on the second WSIS 'Tunis phase' agreements which aimed to put Geneva's Plan of Action into motion as well as to find solutions and reach agreements in the fields

¹ Zeynep Tufekci, 'Engineering the Public: Big Data, Surveillance and Computational Politics', *First Monday*, 19.7 (2014), 1–39 <<https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v19i7.4901>>.

² L. Amore, 'The Politics of Possibility', *Duke University Press*, 2013.

³ David Sangokoya, 'Leveraging Algorithms for DATA-POP ALLIANCE Positive Disruption : WORKING PAPER On Data , Democracy , Society and Statistics Leveraging Algorithms for DATA-POP ALLIANCE Positive Disruption : WORKING PAPER On Data , Democracy , Society', December, 2015.

of internet governance to ensure that the success of Africa's response to the fourth industrial revolution, will include ensuring that people are not left behind as society as the economy become more technologically driven. Therefore, Africans through their national governments and ICT stakeholders should seize the challenge with boldness and resolution by creating capacity building programs, with the potential to be a powerful lever of social, cultural and scientific vitality and of economic development. The alternatives are to do so or risk stagnating in a scientific backwater, isolated from creative streams of social, cultural and economic opportunity⁴.

Mindful of previous commitments made by developing countries and the international community in favor of the development of a common framework for effective governance of internet-enabled technologies, including texts or instruments such as the seventh internet governance forum presided over by the African Union commission in November 2018 under the theme of "Development of the Digital Economy and Emerging Technologies in Africa" which focused on several key areas such as democratization of access to internet and capacity building at all levels to ensure that Africa is ready for the IoT and Big Data usage both for the policy makers, users and innovators⁵. This calls for the civil society, private sector, technical community and governments to convene and coordinate the interests, ideas, people, institutions and resources needed to advocate and to advance digital skills in and for Africa. Existing guidelines and documents which were highlighted in the modules such as 1992 Rio Declaration's Principle 10 which advocates for access to information, access to public information, and access to justice as key pillars of sound environmental governance and sustainable development of the internet⁶⁷ have pushed governments to develop a framework that sets out a shared understanding and means of assessing harm caused by the internet; is capable of dealing with multiple actors and different forms of responsibility; and applies across the full digital life cycle, from conception to deployment. Intergovernmental organizations such as the UN that have been depending on multilateral approach to internet governance have had to enter non-governmental regimes to explore how digital technologies combine, align, contradict and potentially undermine each other and have also joined growing discussions on whether and how the future of digital technologies, or the future with digital technologies, can be crafted such that their development and deployment— from their design to their use, including control, evaluation, auditing, governance—be based on and foster core democratic values such as accountability, transparency, participation, and collaboration⁸.

But what does it look like in practice? In response to the major transformations of our societies due to digital technologies where multiple sectors of our global society are grappling to make sense of how ICT may transform or alter the way we live, work, and relate to one another and our institutions, UNESCO – through its function as a global laboratory of ideas, standard setter, policy

⁴ AOSP, *The Future of Science and Science for the Future* (Pretoria, 2019).

⁵ Milton L. Mueller, 'The Internet Governance Forum', in *Networks and States*, 2018, pp. 1–58 <<https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/8299.003.0008>>.

⁶ Roberto Múkaro Borrero, *Indigenous Peoples and the Information Society : Emerging Uses of ICTs, A Paper Prepared for the First WSIS+10 Review*. (Paris, 2016).

⁷ Steve. Stec, *Putting Rio Principle 10 into Action: An Implementation Guide for the UNEP Bali Guidelines for the Development of National Legislation on Access to Information, Public Participation, and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters* (Nairobi, 2015).

⁸ Sangokoya.

advisor and capacity builder – is playing a leading role in facilitating international cooperation and shaping its future⁹. As learned in the modules, UNESCO, is also raising awareness about implications of AI for societies based on ROAM framework while also developing new and reinforce existing multistakeholder networks at the national and regional levels that can respond to the emerging challenges of digital technologies through co-creation. Governments on the other hand have begun to increasingly playing a major role in¹⁰

- Leveraging AI to promote quality education with a special focus on STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths), scientific research and innovation, as well as to continue to strengthen education for citizenship based on values, rights and duties.
- Promoting an appropriate dialogue with different social actors, scientific communities and the private sector to develop an ethical framework that ensures an adequate protection of autonomy, privacy, non-stigmatization, non-discrimination and human dignity.
- Promoting AI in the bid to build inclusive knowledge societies, guaranteeing access to information for all, freedom of expression and the protection of personal data

Groups of interest engaged in ensuring a more equitable information society, with full, effective, and meaningful participation of Africans include;

- Academic researchers - They have been on the front lines in examining the unforeseen consequences of technology. In particular, the Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency community play a leading role.
- Civil society - These organizations keep up with the potential impact of internet on human rights. Their participation revolve around how to increase the capacity of CSOs to effectively engage in internet debates and bring human rights and accountability to the center of these conversations.
- Legal practitioners - human rights law provide a right to remedy. But in an Internet context, remedy can be difficult to realize. Their discussion lead to a series of questions, such as, how do you remediate for an individual for group harms? How does one define the harms caused by automated systems and identify who is responsible? Are there lessons we can gain from criminal law or product liability? How do you respond to the violation if the use of Internet is in the context of war? How can you remediate what you cannot readily see or know?¹¹

⁹ UNESCO, 'Steering AI and Advanced ICTs for Knowledge Societies Human Rights Implications', 2018 <https://en.unesco.org/system/files/unesco-steering_ai_for_knowledge_societies.pdf> [accessed 15 October 2019].

¹⁰ DST, *DRAFT White Paper on Science, Technology and Innovation*, TAPPI Journal (South Africa, 2018), xvii <<https://doi.org/10.32964/tj17.09>>.

¹¹ accessnow, 'A DIGITAL RIGHTS APPROACH TO THE TECH ACCORD AND THE DIGITAL GENEVA CONVENTION', 2018 <<https://www.accessnow.org/cms/assets/uploads/2018/08/DGC-tech-accord-human-rights.pdf>> [accessed 15 October 2019].

- Funding organizations - financial investment and equitable partnerships are needed to sustain conversations around digital governance and other innovative initiatives

A multi-stakeholder model that is needed in Africa to promote the digital inclusivity is one that supports scientists in pursuit of the highest levels of excellence, in both curiosity-driven and application-driven research; supports social and grassroots innovations and; creates and supports networks of engagement between scientists through national internet governance forums and other societal actors in digital innovation and in addressing local, national and international issues of major public concern.

Inadequate and non-collaborative means of digital agenda setting for the continent, insufficient policy coherence and coordination, weak partnerships with and between digital actors (particularly the inadequate involvement of civil society), inadequate high-level science, engineering and technical skills for the economy, an undersized research system, a poor environment for innovation, and significant levels of underfunding are the main factors constraining Africa to be ready for the explosion of internet usage both for the policy makers, users and innovators.

Opportunities and Risks: Grasping a double edged sword

Viewed positively or negatively, ICTs are powerful tools that offer opportunities to link communities, even in the most remote regions, to each other and to the rest of the world¹². Across Africa, the majority of innovative digital initiatives are very recent or still in development. Additionally, there are limited concrete legislative or regulatory initiatives being implemented. This is not to say however that digital governance operates in a deregulated environment¹³. Legal frameworks such as fundamental rights, national laws on non-discrimination, consumer protection legislation, competition law, safety standards still apply. However, obstacles to connectivity still remain, including poor or absent basic infrastructure (electricity, hardware, etc.), high connectivity costs, inadequate bandwidth, or poor, unreliable service and limited budget allocations for IT maintenance and lifecycle. Understanding the internet and its impact on public discourse, then, requires thinking not simply about how it works, where it's deployed, or what animates it financially. It requires examining why the internet is being looked to as a credible knowledge logic, how it falls apart and repaired, and where political assumptions might not only be etched into its' design, but also constitutive of its' widespread use and legitimacy.

From the internet origins as a U.S.-based research vehicle, as learned in module one of this course, the internet has rapidly become an international medium for commerce, education and communication. This has been facilitated, in part, by open-source ethos that encourages collaboration and experimentation. The Internet Engineering Task Force has taken the lead in developing open standards and protocol that have been the base of the internet's continuity and stability hence allowing devices, services, and applications to be interoperable across a wide and

¹² Paul. Resta, 'ICTs and Indigenous People: UNESCO Institute for Information Technologies in Education Policy Brief', June, 2011.

¹³ Philip Napoli, 'Social Media and the Public Interest: Governance of News Platforms in the Realm of Individual and Algorithmic Gatekeepers', *Telecommunications Policy*, 39.9 (2014).

dispersed network of networks. The implications of this democratization are profound. The fact that open source tools are freely available promotes individual exploration, particularly in a research context. For instance, the development and widespread use of artificial intelligence and machine learning has been facilitated by availability of open source datasets in GitHub¹⁴ with no paper work needed to access them in order to train machine algorithms at the data input level¹⁵ and development of free open source software (FOSS) such as R¹⁶ by the data science community with codes openly shared to encourage improvements. StackExchange is a site where open source community members ask questions and receive help from other community members¹⁷. The time to problem remediation using a site like StackExchange is far shorter than even the best, most expensive support contract for propriety software. A researcher that is having a problem with R package will almost assuredly find someone who has had a similar problem, and a plethora of contributed solutions using the social networking venues almost instantly. The quality of various solution varies and there are some methods like voting that the venue employs to try and help identify the best solutions, but no professional support contract can provide the almost instantaneous remediation opportunity that the open source community does for popular technologies. Put another way, without these people and projects, AI as we know it could not exist. This has led to emergence of initiatives such as Data Science Africa¹⁸, Makerere University AI research group¹⁹ and Deep Learning Indaba²⁰ as hubs for machine learning research in Africa.

Long before the coronavirus spread outside Wuhan province in China, scientist were able to sequence the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2019 genome and made it public using open source tools and open access journals for purposes of literature review for the research community. Across the globe, scientist downloaded it and then begun to isolate antibodies while virologist and computational biologists were using high through-put technologies to analyze its structure and search for existing drugs that might work against it. Insights were then drawn from aggregated data through utilization of big data and artificial intelligence techniques, which were then made public and shareable, and this played a crucial role in understanding the virus and developing measures to contain it. Because of these open source tools and community, scientific research in understanding the virus has been at a really breathtaking speed with vaccine development already in the final stages for human use.

These initiatives are critical to the development of common standards on open data that can guide the private and public sectors on how to provide open access to data sets, ensuring that more data

¹⁴ GitHub, 'GitHub Is a Website for Code Management Built on Top of the (Open Source) Git Version Control System.'

¹⁵ Tom Davis, 'Open Data- Algorithms and AI', *Cape Town and Ottawa: Africa Minds and International Development Research Centre*, The State of Open Data: Histories and Horizons, 2019 <<https://doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.2677813>>.

¹⁶ R Core Team, 'R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing' (Vienna, Austria, 2020) <<https://www.r-project.org/>>.

¹⁷ Katie Malone and Rich Wolski, 'Doing Data Science on the Shoulders of Giants : The Value of Open Source Software for the Data Science Community', 2020, 1–17 <<https://doi.org/10.1162/99608f92.268cc8e4>>.

¹⁸ DSA, 'Data Science Africa' <<http://www.datascienceafrica.org/>> [accessed 20 August 2020].

¹⁹ 'Makerere University AI Research Group' <<http://air.ug/>> [accessed 20 August 2020].

²⁰ Deep learning Indaba, 'Together We Build African Artificial Intelligence', March, 2019.

becomes available to the public, while respecting privacy and confidentiality²¹. Central to the implementation of open data are robust human rights and governance frameworks to enhance trust in technology and data use, while ensuring inclusion²².

Exploring the notion of the internet and algorithms enables us to see how digital technologies also play a part in social ordering processes, both in terms of how the internet is used to promote certain visions of calculative objectivity and also in relation to the wider governmentalities that this concept might be used to open-up²³. But how should we approach the internet in the first place? Should we treat it as lines of code, as objects, or should we see it as social processes in which the social world is embodied in the substrate of the code?²⁴ In the modules, we are introduced to internet infrastructures- physical layer, internet layer, and application layer. The application layer, which enables users to interact with the internet, host a rapidly growing number of internet software's and applications that are built using algorithms. While the term "algorithm" has a precise technical meaning, it has entered everyday discourse as "the things computers do."²⁵ In computer science, an algorithm is a step-by-step set of operations to be performed²⁶. This description makes this process seem neutral, objective, isolated, and reflective of reality. It is important to consider who is included in this new configuration, who is not, and how this is like or unlike previous instantiations.

The risks of having the provision of knowledge through the use of ICT technologies,²⁷ is that, we are left vulnerable to the choices, methods, and subjectivities made by the algorithms. Sometimes this is a positive, providing expertise, editorial acumen, refined taste. But we are also wary of the intervention, of human failings and vested interests, and find ourselves with only secondary mechanisms of social trust by which to vouch for what is true and relevant. Algorithmic procedures are unavoidably selective, emphasizing some information and discarding others, and the choices may be consequential. There is the distinct possibility of error, bias, manipulation, laziness, commercial or political influence, or systemic failures. The selection process can always be an opportunity to curate for reasons other than relevance: for propriety, for commercial or institutional self-interest, or for political gain²⁸.

²¹ Science International, 'Open Data in a Big Data World', ed. by International Social International Council for Science (ICSU) and The World Academy of Sciences (TWAS). InterAcademy Partnership (IAP) Science Council (ISSC) (Paris, 2015), pp. 1–17 <www.science-international.org>.

²² UN, 'Roadmap for Digital Cooperation', June, 2020.

²³ David Beer, 'The Social Power of Algorithms', *Information Communication and Society*, 20.1 (2017), 1–13 <<https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2016.1216147>>.

²⁴ Prof Paul N Edwards, 'POLITICS OF DATA ALGORITHMIC CULTURE , BIG DATA , AND', 2018, 1–7.

²⁵ Robyn Caplan and Danah Boyd, 'Who Controls the Public Sphere in an Era of Algorithms: Mediation, Automation, Power', 2016.

²⁶ Finale Doshi-velez and Mason Kortz, 'Accountability of AI Under the Law : The Role of Explanation', 2013, 1–15.

²⁷ Brent Barron and Rebecca Finlay, 'ACCOUNTABILITY IN AI Promoting Greater Social Trust', 2018.

²⁸ Tarleton Gillespie, '9 The Relevance of Algorithms PROPERTY OF MIT PRESS', *Light* 1999, 2013, 167–94.

Mitigating Digital Harms: ROAM Approach

A useful approach proposed for internet governance in this paper is UNESCO's Internet Universality ROAM principles²⁹. These principles urge that digital development be aligned with human Rights such as freedom of expression, privacy and equality; Openness with regards to knowledge, open data as well as open and pluralistic markets; Accessibility in regard to research, human resources, access to data, multilingualism and hardware; and Multi-stakeholder governance to guide the ensemble of values, norms, policies, regulations, codes and ethics that govern the development and use of the internet³⁰. This approach does not suggest that ROAM principles offers a panacea. Rather, the argument is that ROAM approach to internet governance offers an organizing framework for the design, development and deployment of internet, and identifies the factors that states, businesses, civil society and academic researchers should take into consideration in order to avoid undermining, or violating, human/digital rights. This is a framework which is capable of accommodating other approaches to internet governance — including technical solutions—and which can grow and be built on as ROAM itself develops.

The principle of human rights will check for constitutional or legal guarantee of freedom of artistic expression and existence of a constitutional or legal framework, including oversight arrangements, which is consistent with international and regional rights agreements, laws and standards, and evidence that it is respected and enforced by government and other competent authorities. The principle of openness will ensure existence of a legal framework for access to open data which is consistent with international norms and privacy requirements. The principle of accessibility will check for policy concerning school curricula, including media and information literacy, intercultural dialogue and training in ICT skills including the number of registered domains (including ccTLDs, gTLDs³⁵² and IDNccTLDs), and trend where available. A multi-stakeholder approach will ensure the existence of arrangements for multistakeholder consultation and involvement in national policymaking institutions and processes concerned with the evolution and use of the Internet, membership of and active participation in ICANN's Governmental Advisory Committee (GAC) and existence of national IGF and/or other multistakeholder forum concerned with Internet governance.

A Seat for Youths at the Negotiating Table

The urgency for digital governance is now well understood and the debate is still out there on whether a governance system will place internet on the governed or governing role. As a consequence of impoverished socioeconomic positions, many youths are distinctly disadvantaged with regard to digital information access and distribution, whether residing in developed or

²⁹ *Steering Ai and Advanced ICTs* <https://en.unesco.org/system/files/unesco-steering_ai_for_knowledge_societies.pdf> [accessed 15 October 2019].

³⁰ UNESCO.

developing countries³¹. The Geneva Plan of Action identified eighteen areas of activity in which governments, civil society entities, businesses, and international organizations could work together toward achieving the potential of ICTs for development. This offers an opportunity for youths to be considered full partners across all of the Plan's Action Lines including implementation of Action Line C8³², which presents an ongoing opportunity for youths to partner with UNESCO, as it focuses on specific issues of mutual concern, including cultural diversity and identity, linguistic diversity, and local content. Ultimately, Action Line C8 seeks to ensure that access to technology, information and knowledge is inclusive of everyone including youths.

Way forward.

Digital governance calls for a comprehensive set of regulatory standards, physical infrastructure and digital systems to capture the benefits of the digital revolution for the SDGs while avoiding the many potential pitfalls. An effective digital governance in Africa will therefore require;

- Universal access to high-quality, low-cost mobile broadband.
- Measures to promote digital inclusion, skills, privacy protection and universal identity. These include the digitization of government facilities, universal public online identity for official purposes, income redistribution to address income inequalities, tax and regulatory systems to avoid the monopolization of Internet services and big data, online data governance and interoperability provisions, and democratic oversight of cutting-edge technologies.
- Countries to harness the digital revolution to attain SDGs, including through the digitization of healthcare and education, online finance and payments, and supporting public goods.
- Strengthening of public institutions to govern and shape digital innovations towards sustainable development.

Ministries of science and technology as well as telecommunications will need to coordinate closely with other parts of government and stakeholders—particularly through public–private partnerships—to anticipate and manage the deep societal changes that are both triggered by and needed for the digital revolution, particularly regarding inequalities, the future of work and how artificial intelligence may affect societal decision making. With corporations and governments increasingly eager to rely on data, data emitters and subjects should be incentivized to demand greater direct control over their data—to weigh in on how, by whom and for what purpose it is used³³.

³¹ the Report of WSIS Parallel Event, *Indigenous Peoples and the Information Society: Toward an International Indigenous Portal*, 2005 <www.un.org/esa/socdev/%0Aunpfii/documents/report_en.pdf>.

³² ITU, 'WSIS Implementation by Action Line', 2003 <www.itu.int/net/wsis/%0Aimplementation/> [accessed 20 August 2020].

³³ Lorna McGregor, Daragh Murray, and Vivian Ng, 'International Human Rights Law as a Framework for Algorithmic Accountability', *International and Comparative Law Quarterly*, 68.2 (2019), 309–43 <<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0020589319000046>>.